

The Relationship between Early Complementary Feeding and Nutritional Status and Incidence of Diarrhea in Infants Aged 0-6 Months at the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center in 2022

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of early complementary feeding on the nutritional status and incidence of diarrhea in infants aged 0-6 months at the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center in August 2022. Employing an observational analytic approach with a cross-sectional design, the study sampled 47 infants using simple random sampling techniques. Data were collected through questionnaires and measurements, and analyzed using Chi-square tests ($p < 0.05$). The study found a significant relationship between early complementary feeding and poor nutritional status ($p = 0.048$) as well as the incidence of diarrhea ($p = 0.029$) in infants. These findings underscore the importance of adhering to recommended feeding guidelines to improve infant health outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Infancy is a pivotal stage in human development, marked by rapid growth and development that culminates at the age of 24 months. Achieving optimal health outcomes during this 'golden period' is contingent upon appropriate nutritional intake from birth through the first two years (Mufida et al., 2017). However, global data from the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2017 revealed that only 40% of infants are exclusively breastfed, while the remaining 60% are introduced to non-exclusive breastfeeding before reaching six months of age. This underscores the low prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding across various countries, including Indonesia (Arsi & Afdhal, 2023). The decline in exclusive breastfeeding rates is not confined to developed nations; it is a global issue affecting developing countries as well (A Halil et al., 2017).

According to a 2018 report by the Indonesian Ministry of Health, the prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding was 9.6% for infants aged 0-1 months, 16.7% for those aged 2-3 months, and 43.9% for those aged 4-5 months (KEMENKES RI, 2018). Breast milk, often supplemented with complementary foods, is the recommended primary source of nutrition for children up to two years of age. It contains a balanced mix of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, salts, minerals, and vitamins, along with antibodies that bolster the immune system (Arsi & Afdhal, 2023). However, the early introduction of complementary foods is prevalent and poses health risks, including increased incidences of infections like diarrhea, respiratory issues, allergies, and growth disorders (Eka P et al., 2017).

Good nutrition is foundational for health, affecting immune function, disease susceptibility, and overall growth and development (Afdhal et al., 2023). Several factors influence nutritional status, including early initiation of complementary feeding, household income, healthcare practices, and family caregiving patterns (Rifaul, 2018). Diarrhea, endemic in Indonesia, poses a significant risk to infants and has been on the rise globally. According to WHO data from 2019, there are approximately 1.7 billion cases of infant diarrhea annually, resulting in about 525,000 infant deaths. The Indonesian Basic Health Research (Riskesdas) report from 2018 indicates that the prevalence of diarrhea is higher among toddlers, with 11.4% or roughly 47,764 cases in males and 10.5% or about 45,855 cases in females (KEMENKES RI, 2018).

Recent data from the Palembang City Health Department in 2021 revealed alarming rates of early complementary feeding, poor nutritional status, and diarrhea cases, particularly in the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center's jurisdiction. Specifically, 299 individuals were affected in the Makrayau area, followed by 230 in the Gandus area, 250 in the 1 Ulu area, 270 in the 3/4 Ulu area, and 280 in the 7 Ulu area. In terms of nutritional status, 4% were severely undernourished, 43% were undernourished, 30% were at risk of being overweight, 7% were extremely stunted, and 1% had severe malnutrition, while 34% were slightly malnourished. Diarrhea cases accounted for 1.46% or 50 cases. In 2022, the 7 Ulu Community Health Center in Palembang reported 47 cases involving early complementary feeding, nutritional status, and

diarrhea. Given the compelling issues outlined above, this research aims to investigate the relationship between early complementary feeding and both the nutritional status and incidence of diarrhea in infants aged 0-6 months at the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center in 2022.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Complementary Breastfeeding Food is a food or drink containing nutrients that is given to infants or children aged 6-24 months to meet their nutritional needs beyond breast milk. MP-ASI serves as a transitional food from breast milk to family meals. The introduction and administration of MP-ASI should be done gradually, both in form and quantity, in accordance with the infant's capabilities (Mufida et al., 2017). Early MP-ASI is additional food given to infants under the age of 6 months, besides breast milk (Prawesti, 2017).

The objectives of administering Complementary Breastfeeding Food include: 1) Supplementing nutrients that may be lacking due to the increasing nutritional needs as the child ages, 2) Developing the infant's ability to accept a variety of foods with different forms, textures, and flavors, 3) Enhancing the infant's ability to chew and swallow, and 4) Helping the infant adapt to foods that contain high levels of energy (Molika, 2017).

Early Complementary Breastfeeding Food is food or drink given to infants aged 0-6 months (Nurwiah, 2017). According to Molika (2018), starting Complementary Breastfeeding Food too early is not recommended because: 1) Breast milk can be replaced by other liquids or foods that are less nutritious, 2) A decrease in the baby's sucking demand due to satiety from MP-ASI can lead to a reduction in the mother's breast milk supply, 3) There is an increased risk of infection due to exposure to non-sterile baby food, 4) The infant may not yet be able to digest certain foods properly, and 5) Early exposure to certain foods can trigger allergies.

Nutritional status is a crucial element in shaping overall health. Nutritional status refers to the condition resulting from the balance between nutrient intake from food and the body's nutritional needs (Wiyono et al., 2017). For infants, this status is determined by the equilibrium between nutrient intake and the body's nutritional requirements from food. Nutritional issues can arise due to various factors such as economic limitations, education, family occupation, poor environment, and lack of maternal knowledge.

Diarrhea is a disease syndrome characterized by changes in the form and consistency of stool, transitioning to a liquid state, and an increase in the frequency of bowel movements to three times or more per day. In other words, diarrhea is the passage of stool that is abnormal and liquid, accompanied by a frequency greater than usual. Infants are said to have diarrhea if they have more than three bowel movements, while neonates are said to have diarrhea if they have more than four bowel movements (Prawesti, 2017).

Risk factors for diarrhea in infants, according to Pangesti (2019), include: 1) Behavioral factors such as not providing exclusive breastfeeding, giving MP-ASI too early, using a baby bottle, not practicing handwashing with soap before breastfeeding/feeding, after defecation, and after cleaning a child's defecation,

and 2) Environmental factors such as inadequate clean water supply, lack of sanitation facilities, and poor personal and environmental hygiene. In addition to these risk factors, there are several patient factors that can increase the tendency for diarrhea, such as malnutrition, immunodeficiency, and measles. According to Hartono (2019), complementary food should be given when the baby is 6 months old. Infants aged 0-6 months are susceptible to diarrhea because the lactose enzyme in the intestines is not yet perfect, making it difficult to break down bacteria, leading to infant diarrhea (Pangesti, 2017).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a cross-sectional design, meaning that measurements of both independent and dependent variables are conducted only once at a specific point in time. The research was carried out in August 2022 at Puskesmas 7 Ulu Palembang. As for the population and sample, the study focuses on infants aged 0-6 months who have been given early complementary breastfeeding and have issues related to nutritional status and diarrhea in the Puskesmas 7 Ulu Palembang area. The total population consists of 47 individuals, and a total sampling technique was used, meaning all members of the population were included in the sample.

RESEARCH RESULT

The following are the results of research conducted in the working area of the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center in 2022. This description consists of univariate and bivariate analyzes which explain the characteristics and variables related to early supplementation breastfeeding food, nutrition status and diarrhea and the relationship between early supplementation breastfeeding food, nutrition status and the incidence of diarrhea.

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Age, Education, Occupation, Early Supplementation Breatfeeding Food, Nutrition Status and Diarrhea

Variable distribution	F	%
Age		
Mean	27	
Median	27	
Modus	25	
Education	47	100
Elementary School	0	0
Middle School	6	12,8
High School	24	51,1
Collage	17	36,2
Not in School	0	0
Occupation	47	100
Farmer	2	4,8
Merchant	4	8,5
Civil Servant	4	8,5
Private Employee	23	48,9
Housewife	14	29,8
Early Complementary Breastfeeding Food		
Granted	35	74,5
Not Granted	12	25,5
Nutrition Status	47	100
Malnutrition	4	8,5
Undernutrition	34	72,3
Adequate Nutrition	9	19,1
Diarrhea		
Yes	39	83
No	8	17

Table 1 shows that the average age of mothers is 27 years, with the youngest being 19 years old and the oldest being 35 years old. The majority of mothers have a high school education, with 24 of them (51.1%), while the fewest have a junior high school education, with 6 mothers (12.8%). Most mothers work in the private sector, totaling 23 mothers (48.9%) in the 7 Ulu Community Health Center's working area, whereas the fewest work as farmers, with 2 mothers (4.8%). The majority of mothers provide early complementary feeding (MP-ASI) to their infants, accounting for 35 infants (74.5%), while 12 infants (25.5%) do not receive early complementary feeding. Furthermore, the majority of infants are in a state of undernutrition, with 34 infants (72.3%), while the fewest have severe malnutrition, totaling 4 infants (8.5%), and good nutrition, numbering 9 (19.1%), in the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center's working area.

Table 2. The relationship between early complementary breastfeeding and nutritional status in infants aged 0-6 months

No	Early Complementary Breastfeeding Food	Nutrition Status						Total		P Value
		Malnutrition		Undernutrition		Adequate Nutrition		F	%	
		F	%	F	%	F	%			
1.	Granted	4	8,5	27	57,4	4	8,5	35	74,5	0,048
2.	Not Granted	0	0	7	14,9	5	10,6	12	25,5	
Amount		4	8,5	34	72,3	9	19,1	47	100	

Based on Table 2, it can be observed that out of the 35 mothers who provided early complementary feeding (MP-ASI), the majority experienced severely malnourished nutritional status in their infants, totaling 27 infants (57.4%). Meanwhile, among the 12 mothers who did not provide early complementary feeding, the majority of their infants experienced undernutrition, with 7 infants (14.9%). The results from the table, using Chi-square analysis, indicate valid statistical results with a obtained p-value of $0.048 < \alpha = 0.05$, which means that the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted, suggesting a relationship between early complementary feeding and the nutritional status of infants aged 0-6 months in the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center's working area.

Table 3. The relationship between early complementary breastfeeding and diarrhea in infants aged 0-6 months

No	Early Complementary Breastfeeding Food	Diarrhea				Total		P Value
		Malnutrition		Undernutrition		F	%	
		F	%	F	%			
1.	Granted	32	68,1	3	6,4	35	74,5	0,029
2.	Not Granted	7	14,9	5	10,6	12	25,5	
Amount		39	83	8	17	47	100	

Based on Table 3, it can be observed that out of the 35 mothers who provided early complementary feeding (MP-ASI), the majority experienced diarrhea in their infants, totaling 32 infants (68.9%). Meanwhile, among the 12 mothers who did not provide early complementary feeding, the majority of their infants also experienced diarrhea, with 7 infants (14.9%). The results from the table, using Chi-square analysis, indicate valid statistical results with an obtained p-value of $0.029 < \alpha = 0.05$, which means that the null hypothesis (H_0)

is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H2) is accepted, suggesting a relationship between early complementary feeding and the incidence of diarrhea in infants aged 0-6 months in the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center's working area.

DISCUSSION

The relationship between early complementary breastfeeding and nutritional status in infants aged 0-6 months

The relationship between early complementary feeding and the nutritional status of infants aged 0-6 months in the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center's working area yielded a p-value of $0.048 < \alpha = 0.05$. This indicates that there is a relationship between early complementary feeding and the nutritional status of infants aged 0-6 months in the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center's working area. From the research results, most of the 35 mothers who provided MP-ASI had infants with undernutrition, with 27 infants having poor nutritional status, and 4 infants with severe malnutrition. Meanwhile, among the 12 mothers who did not provide MP-ASI, 7 infants had undernutrition, and 5 infants had normal nutritional status.

According to Molika (2017), early introduction of complementary feeding can lead to allergies in infants to certain food substances. This condition arises due to the permeable nature of an infant's gut, allowing foreign proteins to pass through easily. Malnutrition or growth disorders can occur if the provided food lacks nutritional value, leading to Protein Energy Malnutrition (PEM), or obesity if the food is excessively high in calories (Molika, 2017). According to Riksani (2017), the key to initiating complementary feeding is the baby's readiness to accept it. Signs of a baby's readiness for complementary feeding include the ability to hold and control their head well, sitting without support, and paying attention to the mother while she is eating and attempting to reach for food (Riksani, 2017).

The findings of this research are supported by the results of a study conducted by Risa Wargiana (2018) on the Early Introduction of Complementary Feeding and Nutritional Status in Infants Aged 0-6 Months in the Rowotengah Community Health Center's working area in Jember Regency. It concluded that early introduction of complementary feeding often has a direct impact on infants, including digestive disturbances such as diarrhea, difficulty in bowel movements, vomiting, and feeding difficulties when infants show interest in family food, such as paying attention to the mother while she is eating and attempting to reach for food (Riksani, 2017).

There are several factors that influence nutritional status, including supplementary feeding programs, income levels, health maintenance, and family caregiving patterns. It can be observed that a majority, totaling 23 mothers, are employed, and this affects the caregiving patterns of mothers towards their infants. The high number of working mothers results in reduced breastfeeding for infants. Adequate production of breast milk requires hormones such as oxytocin and prolactin. Lack of attention and maternal care

towards the baby can impact breastfeeding, leading to disturbances in infant nutrition.

From the explanation above, it is evident that the majority of mothers have introduced early complementary feeding (MP-ASI) to their infants before the age of 6 months. Early introduction of complementary feeding can pose health risks, both immediate and long-term. Immediate risks occur when infants are introduced to complementary foods early, while long-term risks may become apparent later on. Long-term risks of early complementary feeding include obesity, hypertension, atherosclerosis, and food allergies. Feeding disturbances can arise because excessive complementary feeding may make the baby feel full, reducing the desire to breastfeed. Inadequate breast milk intake can result in health problems for infants because breast milk contains essential nutrients that babies require. Health department standards specify that infants aged 0-6 months only need breast milk as it contains proteins, fats, vitamins, minerals, water, and enzymes necessary for their development. Inappropriate complementary feeding in terms of timing and the baby's needs can have an impact on the baby's health and nutritional status.

Nutrition plays a crucial role in the human life cycle. Malnutrition in infants can lead to growth and development disorders that, if not addressed early, can persist into adulthood. Therefore, nutritional problems are fundamentally rooted in behavioral issues, particularly in the understanding of nutrition. To address this issue, efforts should focus on providing education at local health posts (posyandu) or counseling during visits to health centers. Additionally, the roles of posyandu cadres, nurses, and other healthcare workers are crucial in providing information to mothers, emphasizing exclusive breastfeeding for the first 6 months. After the baby reaches 6 months, complementary feeding can be introduced. Through information and education, it is hoped that mothers' awareness will increase, particularly in providing appropriate complementary feeding and ensuring the nutritional status of infants aged 0-6 months.

The relationship between early complementary breastfeeding and diarrhea in infants aged 0-6 months

The relationship between early complementary feeding and the incidence of diarrhea in infants aged 0-6 months in the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center's working area yielded a p-value of $0.029 < \alpha = 0.05$. This indicates that there is a relationship between early complementary feeding and the incidence of diarrhea in infants aged 0-6 months in the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center's working area. From the research results, among mothers who provided complementary feeding, 32 infants experienced diarrhea, while 3 infants did not experience diarrhea due to inappropriate early complementary feeding. Early complementary feeding can lead to digestive system disturbances and growth disorders in infants.

The findings of this research are supported by the results of a study conducted by Lutfi Wahyuni (2015) on the Provision of Complementary Feeding in Infants Aged 0-6 Months and the Incidence of Diarrhea in Pacet

Village, Pacet Sub-district, Mojokerto Regency. It concluded that early introduction of complementary feeding can lead to absorption disorders in the intestines. The results are further supported by the research conducted by Mufida Annisa Rahmawati (2021) on the relationship between early complementary feeding and the incidence of diarrhea in infants aged 0-6 months, which concluded that early introduction of complementary feeding can result in digestive disturbances such as diarrhea. Infants under 6 months of age have an immature digestive system and are not ready to digest solid foods. If introduced prematurely, this can lead to unexpected reactions such as digestive problems, constipation, and gas. These findings are also supported by Maidartati's research (2021) on the relationship between early complementary feeding and the incidence of diarrhea in infants aged 0-6 months, which identified factors contributing to diarrhea as maternal knowledge, maternal attitudes, history of early complementary feeding, history of exclusive breastfeeding, and hygiene and sanitation (Annisa Rahmawati & Ningrum, 2021).

Infants under 6 months of age have an immature digestive system, and complementary foods contain a high concentration of various nutrients. Malabsorption that occurs can increase osmotic pressure in the intestinal cavity, leading to the shift of water and electrolytes into the intestinal cavity, resulting in diarrhea. According to Proverawati's theory (2010), the basic mechanism leading to diarrhea is osmotic disturbances caused by the presence of food or substances that cannot be absorbed by the body, leading to increased osmotic pressure in the intestinal cavity. Excessive contents in the intestinal cavity stimulate the intestine to expel its contents, resulting in diarrhea (Proverawati, 2017).

From the above explanation, it is evident that diarrhea can occur because mothers have introduced early complementary feeding to infants under 6 months of age. They may not be aware that one of the consequences of early complementary feeding can be diarrhea in infants. The majority of mothers who introduced early complementary feeding to infants under 6 months tended to have infants with diarrhea compared to mothers who did not introduce early complementary feeding to infants aged 0-6 months. This is because infants under 6 months of age have a weak digestive system and cannot digest foreign or complementary foods properly, leading to digestive system disturbances. Therefore, nurses and other healthcare workers can provide health education to the community in the 7 Ulu Palembang Community Health Center's working area to inform mothers about the risks of early complementary feeding and its potential consequences, including diarrhea. Through educational activities at the community level, such as posyandu (integrated health posts) sessions, mothers can gain knowledge about complementary feeding, types of complementary foods, the consequences of early complementary feeding, as well as information about the causes and prevention of diarrhea. Health education activities can increase mothers' awareness and knowledge about the importance of proper complementary feeding and the prevention of diarrhea in infants aged 0-6 months.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, it was found that the highest age among the mothers of respondents was 35 years old, with the majority of them having completed high school education (51.1%) and working in the private sector (48.9%). Furthermore, 74.5% of infants received early complementary feeding, with 72.3% of them classified as underweight, 8.5% as severely underweight, and 19.1% as having a normal nutritional status. Additionally, 83% of infants experienced diarrhea, while 17% did not. The research results also indicated a significant correlation between early complementary feeding and the nutritional status of infants aged 0-6 months in the working area of Puskesmas 7 Ulu Palembang (p-value 0.048), as well as a relationship between early complementary feeding and the occurrence of diarrhea in infants aged 0-6 months in Puskesmas 7 Ulu Palembang (p-value 0.029).

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Data collection through questionnaires is subjective in nature, as the responses in the questionnaires depend on the personal opinions or views of the respondents. The determination of diarrhea occurrence is not a definitive diagnosis based on a precise macroscopic examination but aligns with existing theories. Due to limited time and resources, and a large number of subjects under investigation, data collection was restricted to guided questionnaire completion, and direct interviews were not conducted.

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